

INNOVATIVE USES OF TECHNOLOGY IN PROMOTING SPEAKING SKILLS AMONG LANGUAGE LEARNERS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL TOOLS THROUGH THE LENS OF RECENT INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH

Maftuna Davlatova Kakhramon kizi

3rd year student of Tashkent State pedagogical University named after Nizami, Bunyodkor
st.27.Tashkent 100070, Uzbekistan
e-mail: maftunadavlatova004@gmail.com

Abstract: In today's globalized era the ability to communicate is no longer considered as just an insignificant skill, but also as a remarkable life ability. Accomplishment opens a door to a new way of life accessibilities, including cultural awareness, professional chances, international education, and worthwhile encompassing citizenship. Although all language skills are needed, speaking is often takes the most vital role among the others. It requires learners to be more confident, to process information fluently and build cultural link in real time. As opposed to reading or writing, speaking is considered as spontaneous cooperation - involves psychological challenge in learners' path, especially in non-native languages. This article aimed to compare recent researches to identify challenges which pupils face while integrating tools and investigate the role of digital tools to enhance communication skills of learners' in an education path.

Key words: technology, cultural link, speaking skills, flipped classroom, flipgrid recordings.

1. Introduction

As the importance of oral communication continues to grow, it is essential to use devices related to learners' interests. By taking an action like this educators will achieve their aim more effectively. In the sphere of education, the term "Technology" means to enhance learning experiences. The main purpose of integrating technologies into education is to make this process more engaging and productive. While traditional-teaching methods are still valuable, students feel anxious or self-conscious when it comes to speak in front of the audience. As for that, it may cause to conduct the lesson a bit challenging and learners could not receive enough opportunities to enrich their speaking skills. For example, mobile devices like Duolingo, ELSA speak, and Memrise, or conference tools like Zoom or Google video-chats designed to increase the spoken language in FL context. These applications are considered as a way of fostering oral communication proficiency and to make friends over the world. It also helps to receive feedback from native speakers, practice speaking at their own pace and convenience. That's why integrating these kind of digital tools while language learning process is crucial, besides that above mentioned effective ways, they make learning more interactive, engaging and taking active participation- beyond what traditional methods can provide.

2. Materials and methods

This study compares the international research from different countries of world to define the effective way of developing oral communication skills among the foreign language learners.

1. Research articles were selected based on the following criteria:
 - Focused on developing language skills, especially speaking
 - Digital tools (Duolingo, flipped classroom, Memrise) were used to focus on to strengthen weak points

- All researches were conducted within 5 years, which helps to explore recent digital technologies
- Gives an opportunity to analyze the topic with a graph from different geographical areas of the world (Iraq, Indonesia, etc.)
- 2. The selected articles to compare were the works of:
 - Ahmad (2023) -“ The effectiveness of authentic technology-based materials in developing speaking skills among undergraduate students in Libya”.¹²¹
 - Sim, J. and Ismail, H. (2023) – “ Using digital tools in teaching and learning English: Delving into English language teachers’ perspectives”¹²²
 - Nguyen Thi Doan Trinh & Pham Vu Phi Ho (2022) – “ Effects of using technology to support students in developing speaking skills”¹²³
- 3. A thematic analysis was conducted to define:
 - Instructional strategies (flipped classroom, self-assessment)
 - Digital tools (Zoom, Duolingo, mobile apps)
 - Challenges which students faced while learning

3. Results

The comparative analysis of these above-mentioned researchs aimed to implement shared instructions into a learning diversity. We have seen the results based on this following: digital devices, applied instructional strategies and learning outcomes.

Used digital applications: When we look through the Ahmad’s study, he focused on smartphones, mobile apps like Duolingo and google Meet in order to enhance learner’s, particularly within the Kurdistan regions higher education, spoken language skills. While Sim, J. and Ismail, H. (2023) incorporates video recordings, voice-chats, feedback tools, Nguyen Thi Doan Trinh & Pham Vu Phi Ho (2022) were explored the way of implementing tools like Zoom, Flipgrid and WhatsApp into a learning process.

Instructional Approaches: All mentioned studies conducted learner-centered and interactive approaches. Ahmad used technology-enhanced communicative approach, to apply digital tools into pairs work. Sim, J. and Ismail, H. (2023) implemented a flipped classroom model, where students learn new theme at home by using technologies, and received asynchronized feedback. In contrast, third researchers were implemented task-based learning method incorporating Zoom platform via Flipgrid recordings¹²⁴. By doing this, they supported both fluency and reflection during the practice of oral communication.

Learner outcomes: Each study announces improving students' speeches: while Ahmad (2023) noted that when the students used digital means, students had reduced more confidence and anxiety. Sim, J. and Ismail, H. (2023) found that multivets and reports written by teachers has significantly improved the use of students pronunciation and dictionary. Engagement and Autonomously: Nguyen Thi Doan Trinh & Pham Vu Phi Ho (2022), especially students, especially students, argued their pace and think about the records.

Challenges: When the training shows positive results, each confesses certain opportunities. Ahmad (2023) indicated lack of limited Internet access and lack of digital literacy among some students. Sim, J. and Ismail, H. (2023) outlined that some students were familiar with asynchronous communication, which affected their motivation, Nguyen Thi Doan Trinh & Pham Vu Phi Ho (

¹²¹ Kurdish Studies Apr 2023 Volume: 11, No: 02, pp. 716-729 ISSN: 2051-4883 (Print) | ISSN 2051-4891 (Online) www.KurdishStudies.net Received: May 2023 Accepted: June 2023 DOI:

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¹²² Sim, J. and Ismail, H. (2023) Using Digital Tools in Teaching and Learning English: Delving into English Language Teachers’ Perspectives. *Creative Education*, 14, 2021-2036. doi: [10.4236/ce.2023.1410129](https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2023.1410129).

¹²³ Nguyen, T.D.T., & Pham, V. P. H. (2022). Effects of using technology to support students in developing speaking skills. *International Journal of Language Instruction*, 1(1), 1-8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54855/ijli.22111>

¹²⁴ short, student-recorded video responses used to practice speaking asynchronously.

2022) recorded time constraining live in Zoom and the obstacle to the full effective performance of technical issues.

4. Discussion

The comparative analysis of this framework released that supporting digital devices into language learning process helps to reduce anxiety while speaking and practicing and their own pace, based on the context, tools, and pedagogical model (Ahmad,2023 and Nguyen Thi Doan Trinh & Pham Vu Phi Ho, 2022).

The flipped classroom model was implemented by Sim, J. and Ismail, H. (2023), which helps to develop students speaking proficiency via receiving asynchronous feedback from the educator after learning the given material. It also effects on the improvement students' fluency, vocabulary and also pronunciation.

Besides that, Nguyen Thi Doan Trinh & Pham Vu Phi Ho, 2022) emphasized a learner autonomy and engagement through the usage of mobile applications like Flipgrid and WhatsApp, where students can practice and improve their spoken language skill. It also contributed to the development of the controlled scheduling which motivates students to practice regularly.

Despite the advantages of integrating technologies into the education journey, there is also technical challenges, which learners faced, including internet connection, being unfamiliar with the usage of technology, and not being able to having electronic devices for implementing flipped classroom teaching method.

It is also essential to admit that this study analyzed only three studies, that is why it doesnot fully represent the diversity of experiments, innovations, and difficulties in the usage of technologies.

5. Conclusion

This study identifies the way and effectiveness of integrating technical devices like Zoom, WhatsApp, Flipgrid which helps to develop speaking skills among the foreign language learners. Also it highlights the technical issues and contextual challenges, including technical limitations and gaps in learning journey. This difficulties must be mitigated via implementing new methods into the process, which all learners' can benefit in an honest way. Eventually, it ensures the successful integration of technology is not considered only as a tool, but also the way of life accessibility-cultural awareness, widening horizon and global citizenship. As integrating digital tools continues to develop, future studies should emphasize this learning outcomes more deeper and full of samples.

References

1. “ The effectiveness of authentic technology-based materials in developing speaking skills among undergraduate students in Libya” (Ahmad,2023) <https://kurdishstudies.net/menu-script/index.php/KS/article/view/649/283>
2. “ Using digital tools in teaching and learning English: Delving into English language teachers' prespectives. (Sim, J. and Ismail, H. 2023) <https://i-jli.org/index.php/journal/article/view/18/1>
3. “ Effects of using technology to support students in developing speaking skills” (Nguyen, T.D.T., & Pham, V. P. H; 2022) <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=128787>
4. Implementing Interactive Technology in Developing Speaking Skills in EFL Learners Journal: Scientific Journal of Modern Education and Research, 3(1), 56–64. Matkurbanova, M. (2024).